

Unconfined Compression Strength test

Purpose		Specimens	fiber-stabilized carbide-slag- solidified soil
Size	50×50×50mm	NO.	
test condition		Date	2021.7.12-8.15
test basis	Unconfined Compressive Strength Test Method for Inorganic Binder Stabilized Materials(T0805-		
equipment	Pavement material strength tester		

NO.	Length (mm)	content (%)	age (d)	load (kN)	Unconfined Compression Strength (Mpa)	avaged Unconfined Compression Strength (Mpa)
1	0	0	7	1.849	0.96	0.98
2	0	0	7	1.907	0.99	
3	0	0	7	1.946	1.01	
4	0	0	7	1.984	1.03	
5	0	0	7	1.811	0.94	
6	0	0	7	1.869	0.97	
7	0	0	28	2.986	1.55	
8	0	0	28	3.063	1.59	
9	0	0	28	2.832	1.47	
10	0	0	28	2.870	1.49	
11	0	0	28	2.986	1.55	
12	0	0	28	2.870	1.49	0.99
13	6	0.1	7	1.888	0.98	
14	6	0.1	7	2.023	1.05	
15	6	0.1	7	1.984	1.03	
16	6	0.1	7	1.849	0.96	
17	6	0.1	7	1.869	0.97	
18	6	0.1	7	1.869	0.97	
19	6	0.1	28	2.928	1.52	
20	6	0.1	28	3.025	1.57	
21	6	0.1	28	2.832	1.47	
22	6	0.1	28	3.140	1.63	
23	6	0.1	28	3.294	1.71	
24	6	0.1	28	2.832	1.47	1.03
25	6	0.2	7	2.04209	1.06	
26	6	0.2	7	2.11915	1.1	
27	6	0.2	7	1.868705	0.97	
28	6	0.2	7	1.830175	0.95	
29	6	0.2	7	2.08062	1.08	
30	6	0.2	7	2.00356	1.04	
31	6	0.2	28	3.255785	1.69	
32	6	0.2	28	3.15946	1.64	
33	6	0.2	28	2.96681	1.54	
34	6	0.2	28	3.140195	1.63	
35	6	0.2	28	3.101665	1.61	
36	6	0.2	28	3.140195	1.63	1.04
37	6	0.3	7	1.945765	1.01	
38	6	0.3	7	2.08062	1.08	
39	6	0.3	7	1.907235	0.99	
40	6	0.3	7	1.77238	0.92	
41	6	0.3	7	2.176945	1.13	
42	6	0.3	7	2.08062	1.08	
43	6	0.3	28	3.409905	1.77	
44	6	0.3	28	3.178725	1.65	

45	6	0.3	28	3.12093	1.62	
46	6	0.3	28	3.448435	1.79	
47	6	0.3	28	3.409905	1.77	
48	6	0.3	28	3.39064	1.76	1.73
49	6	0.4	7	1.945765	1.01	
50	6	0.4	7	1.907235	0.99	
51	6	0.4	7	2.08062	1.08	
52	6	0.4	7	1.907235	0.99	
53	6	0.4	7	2.04209	1.06	
54	6	0.4	7	2.08062	1.08	1.04
55	6	0.4	28	3.371375	1.75	
56	6	0.4	28	3.12093	1.62	
57	6	0.4	28	3.063135	1.59	
58	6	0.4	28	3.12093	1.62	
59	6	0.4	28	3.19799	1.66	
60	6	0.4	28	3.409905	1.77	1.67
61	12	0.1	7	1.984295	1.03	
62	12	0.1	7	2.08062	1.08	
63	12	0.1	7	1.84944	0.96	
64	12	0.1	7	1.907235	0.99	
65	12	0.1	7	1.984295	1.03	
66	12	0.1	7	1.907235	0.99	1.01
67	12	0.1	28	2.909015	1.51	
68	12	0.1	28	3.12093	1.62	
69	12	0.1	28	2.88975	1.5	
70	12	0.1	28	3.140195	1.63	
71	12	0.1	28	3.255785	1.69	
72	12	0.1	28	3.101665	1.61	1.59
73	12	0.2	7	1.907235	0.99	
74	12	0.2	7	2.08062	1.08	
75	12	0.2	7	1.88797	0.98	
76	12	0.2	7	1.907235	0.99	
77	12	0.2	7	2.061355	1.07	
78	12	0.2	7	2.00356	1.04	1.03
79	12	0.2	28	3.23652	1.68	
80	12	0.2	28	3.063135	1.59	
81	12	0.2	28	2.986075	1.55	
82	12	0.2	28	3.19799	1.66	
83	12	0.2	28	3.12093	1.62	
84	12	0.2	28	3.178725	1.65	1.63
85	12	0.3	7	1.868705	0.97	
86	12	0.3	7	2.08062	1.08	
87	12	0.3	7	1.907235	0.99	
88	12	0.3	7	2.022825	1.05	
89	12	0.3	7	2.022825	1.05	
90	12	0.3	7	2.061355	1.07	1.04
91	12	0.3	28	3.27505	1.7	
92	12	0.3	28	3.23652	1.68	
93	12	0.3	28	3.101665	1.61	
94	12	0.3	28	3.063135	1.59	
95	12	0.3	28	3.23652	1.68	
96	12	0.3	28	3.23652	1.68	1.66
97	12	0.4	7	2.022825	1.05	
98	12	0.4	7	1.96503	1.02	
99	12	0.4	7	1.96503	1.02	
100	12	0.4	7	2.138415	1.11	
101	12	0.4	7	2.04209	1.06	
102	12	0.4	7	2.061355	1.07	1.06

103	12	0.4	28	3.19799	1.66	
104	12	0.4	28	3.063135	1.59	
105	12	0.4	28	3.140195	1.63	
106	12	0.4	28	3.23652	1.68	
107	12	0.4	28	3.42917	1.78	
108	12	0.4	28	3.178725	1.65	1.67
109	19	0.1	7	2.061355	1.07	
110	19	0.1	7	2.022825	1.05	
111	19	0.1	7	1.868705	0.97	
112	19	0.1	7	1.88797	0.98	
113	19	0.1	7	2.08062	1.08	
114	19	0.1	7	1.907235	0.99	1.02
115	19	0.1	28	3.217255	1.67	
116	19	0.1	28	3.101665	1.61	
117	19	0.1	28	3.00534	1.56	
118	19	0.1	28	3.140195	1.63	
119	19	0.1	28	3.178725	1.65	
120	19	0.1	28	3.0824	1.6	1.62
121	19	0.2	7	1.907235	0.99	
122	19	0.2	7	2.08062	1.08	
123	19	0.2	7	1.88797	0.98	
124	19	0.2	7	1.907235	0.99	
125	19	0.2	7	2.061355	1.07	
126	19	0.2	7	2.00356	1.04	1.03
127	19	0.2	28	3.255785	1.69	
128	19	0.2	28	3.04387	1.58	
129	19	0.2	28	3.101665	1.61	
130	19	0.2	28	3.12093	1.62	
131	19	0.2	28	3.140195	1.63	
132	19	0.2	28	3.23652	1.68	1.64
133	19	0.3	7	1.96503	1.02	
134	19	0.3	7	1.88797	0.98	
135	19	0.3	7	2.022825	1.05	
136	19	0.3	7	2.08062	1.08	
137	19	0.3	7	2.061355	1.07	
138	19	0.3	7	2.061355	1.07	1.05
139	19	0.3	28	3.31358	1.72	
140	19	0.3	28	3.19799	1.66	
141	19	0.3	28	3.19799	1.66	
142	19	0.3	28	3.12093	1.62	
143	19	0.3	28	3.31358	1.72	
144	19	0.3	28	3.39064	1.76	1.69
145	19	0.4	7	2.099885	1.09	
146	19	0.4	7	2.138415	1.11	
147	19	0.4	7	2.04209	1.06	
148	19	0.4	7	2.022825	1.05	
149	19	0.4	7	2.08062	1.08	
150	19	0.4	7	1.907235	0.99	1.06
151	19	0.4	28	3.42917	1.78	
152	19	0.4	28	3.448435	1.79	
153	19	0.4	28	3.178725	1.65	
154	19	0.4	28	3.19799	1.66	
155	19	0.4	28	3.15946	1.64	
156	19	0.4	28	3.409905	1.77	1.72